

Differentiated Instruction in Araling Panlipunan 7 and Academic Performance

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of differentiated instruction on the academic performance of students in Araling. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School, Sta. Cruz South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. The subjects of this study were the 85 grade four pupils – 42 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 43 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of differentiated instruction in Araling Panlipunan 7 has increased the academic performance of grade seven learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Differentiated Instruction.
2. Araling Panlipunan 7.

1. Introduction

Teaching had the image of individuality and isolation. Prior to No Child Left Behind (NCLB) teachers were free to do what they thought was best for their students in their classrooms. Now, because of NCLB, states and districts have a duty to more closely monitor what and how teachers are teaching. Recently there is a huge emphasis on collaboration and integration with other teachers and disciplines (Beecher, 2020). Professional Learning Communities are finding their way into more districts and schools as an attempt to bring teachers together in the planning and teaching process.

When teachers collaborate about lessons, strategies, students, and activities differentiated instruction becomes easier. Other teachers' ideas and insights can be used to differentiate a classroom and help all students become engaged and motivated (DuFour, 2019). Professional Learning Communities is one way to increase the climate of community between teachers, students, and teachers and students which all impacts how classrooms are differentiated (Betts, 2019). Using differentiated instruction as a way of thinking and planning in the classroom, collaboration is key. Teaching should not be in

isolation. To obtain the most benefit out of differentiation and to meet the needs of all students, many minds are needed. Discussing and collaborating frequently with fellow teachers is the key to being effective (Morrison, 2020). This idea of collaboration is supported by Dee (2019). She believes educators have to really know their students academically in order to effectively differentiate instruction to meet all needs. Through collaboration and teacher discussions, methods and activities that will meet the diverse needs in the classroom will be discovered. Teachers have different experiences with teaching and with a variety of students, and those experiences need to be shared in order to have effective differentiated instruction in all classrooms. As classrooms are more diversified and test scores and scoring proficiency is more important, teachers are asked to do the very difficult task of teaching the exact same content to the point of proficiency for each student. Teachers are asked to teach content to a diverse population of students coming from a variety of family backgrounds, prior knowledge, interests, and language ability without leaving any student behind intellectually (Witherell, 2019). Dunn (2020) sums up the feeling among teachers, although teachers have yearned for decades for more responsive and effective methods in addressing students' differences, many children perform daily on the 'margins' of their classrooms - never fully engaged and rarely ever catching a glimpse of their brightest potential. Teachers know what is achievable; teachers have dreams of success for all students in their classrooms but are at a standstill when it comes to what action to take. Differentiated instruction is a way to accomplish that difficult task. Unfortunately, it can be implemented poorly if not completely understood by the teacher. Week after week teachers question why students with learning potential choose to respond below their capacity academically. Week after week teachers wonder why students get less and less motivated to achieve.

And yet week after week, teachers do nothing to change the way things are done in the classroom. Concepts are taught the same way, stories are read in the same fashion, and tests look almost exactly the same week after week, year after year. As the year progresses, teachers begin to question whether the students will be ready and have the necessary skills for the next year. Teachers question whether or not students actually learned anything (Goodnough, 2019). Both students and teachers are bored. Teachers look back over the year and reflect with discouragement on what teaching has become. Teachers know deep down that teaching and learning is not boring; students need to be involved and motivated to achieve. Students feel successful in order to be successful. Students need to be actively drawn into learning to enjoy that learning (Hattie, 2019). In a differentiated classroom this is not the case. Success, involvement, and enjoyment take place because students have a variety of readings to learn particular content, a variety of activities to choose from, and a variety of assessment to demonstrate learning. An important part of differentiating instruction is to make sure all students are learning the same content and mastering the same skill (Mellard, 2020). Classrooms are set up in centers or stations where students move through content and activities at their own pace. Students are able to read stories, relate to characters and situations, and show understanding of standards through a variety of means all geared toward their various learning styles and multiple intelligences. Students are motivated to learn and begin taking control of their own learning while the teacher plays the role of facilitator, able to spend more one-on-one time with the students who need it (Patterson, 2020). In the school where the researcher is currently connected, teachers encounter a diverse range of students, each with their own unique strengths, backgrounds, and learning styles. While this diversity can enrich the educational experience, it also presents

some challenges such as addressing the varying academic needs of students with different abilities. Some students may require additional support or accommodations to succeed, while others may need more advanced materials to be appropriately challenged. Finding the right balance and providing individualized instruction can be a complex task for teacher (Logan, 2019). The situation cited would suggest that using differentiated instruction are beneficial to learners in diverse classroom. Differentiated instruction recognizes that students have different learning styles, abilities, and needs, and aims to meet those individual needs through tailored instruction. This approach is essential as it ensures that all students have equal opportunities to learn and succeed (Simpkins, 2019). In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Sta Cruz National High School, teachers have to look for strategy to make learning happen in diverse learners. The researcher as a teacher exhausts her effort in looking for a strategy to providing multiple pathways for learning and promotes academic growth for all students. Hence, this study of utilizing differentiated instruction to enhance the academic performance of diverse learners of Araling Panlipunan 7.

1.1. *Review of Related Literature—*

1.1.1. *Differentiated Instruction in Social Studies—*Differentiated instruction (DI) is a teaching approach aimed at accommodating the diverse learning needs of students by modifying content, process, and products based on students' readiness, interests, and learning profiles (Doll, 2019; Cohen, 2021; Werderich, 2020). The goal is to provide personalized learning experiences that engage and challenge each student effectively (Brimijoin, 2020).

Several strategies have been identified as effective in implementing DI. Flexible grouping organizes students by their learning needs and abilities, allowing tailored instruction (Mellesse, 2020). Tiered assignments offer tasks at varying complexity levels, ensuring appropri-

ate challenge and engagement for all students (Brookhart, 2021). Learning stations provide diverse activities and allow students to learn at their own pace (Levy, 2019). Learning contracts encourage student ownership of learning through goal-setting and choice (Page, 2021). Curriculum compacting accelerates advanced students through content they have mastered, allowing for more meaningful challenges (Langa, 2020).

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is another key strategy, aiming to remove learning barriers and provide multiple means of representation, expression, and engagement from the start (Santangelo, 2020). Peer tutoring, involving students supporting each other's learning, also promotes collaboration and mutual understanding (Goddard, 2020).

Challenges and Impacts Implementing DI, especially in large classes, poses significant challenges, such as the need for ongoing teacher training and the difficulty of preparing varied daily lessons (Reynolds, 2021; Pettig, 2020). However, studies show that systematic use of DI improves student achievement and engagement (Valiandes, 2019; Kadum-Bošnjak, 2020). Identifying students' learning styles is crucial, as it helps teachers tailor their methods to students' strengths, enhancing academic performance and attitudes toward learning (Tileston, 2020; Wan, 2020).

1.1.2. *Context in Philippine Education—*In the Philippines, traditional education methods often fail to address student diversity, making learning tedious and challenging (Yendol-Hoppey, 2020). The Education for All (EFA) 2015 initiative aims to improve education quality, and DI is proposed as a strategy to cater to varied student needs in overcrowded classrooms (Philippine Education for All, 2015; Gonzalez, 2019).

Overall, while DI requires significant effort from teachers, its benefits in creating an inclusive and effective learning environment are well-

documented. Effective implementation of DI strategies can transform educational practices, particularly in diverse and large classrooms like those in the Philippines .

1.2. Synthesis—The literature review presented above provides an overview of the perspectives and viewpoints of various authors regarding the significance of differentiated instruction that can lead to improve the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 in diverse classroom. While some authors share similar ideas, there are also contrasting statements. These statements will serve as a guide for the researcher in conducting her own study, forming conclusions, and making recommendations. Additionally, the literature review will serve as a framework for the researcher to follow throughout the research process. It will also serve as a reference for the researcher to support and justify any findings that arise from the statistical analysis and interpretation.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study is anchored on the Multiple Intelligences Theory of Gardner (1983). According to Gardner multiple intelligences are the different ways people learn and process information best. There are eight different multiple intelligences: verbal linguistic, logical-mathematical, visual-spatial, musical, kinesthetic, interpersonal, intrapersonal, and naturalist. Gardner further emphasized that multiple intelligences require dif-

ferent learning styles. Learning styles are how students take information in effectively, the environment while learning, and the method information is then reproduced to show learning. If students learn information differently, then teachers should present and assess what is being taught differently based on those diverse intelligences and styles. Teachers need to be able to teach the necessary content, using different strategies for how students will learn content and what they will use to teach content, while ensuring success for each individual student in the classroom. Through the use of multiple intelligences and different learning styles all students will have a chance to see themselves succeed in school which should lead to an increase in motivation. Differentiating instruction, through the use of a variety of motivational strategies, activities, and assessments, builds upon these ideas of multiple intelligences and learning styles while staying faithful to all students with the same curricular goals and mastery of the same content standards. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of this experimental research. The action initiated is the use of differentiated instruction and it hopefully affects the Araling Panlipunan 7 academic performance. It is hoped that through the use of this approach, the academic performance of the students will be increased.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The general purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of differentiated instruction on the aca-

ademic performance of students in Araling Panlipunan 7 . Specifically, this research study aimed to answer the following research objectives.

- (1) What is the pretest score of Araling Panlipunan 7 students both controlled and experimental groups before the implementation of differentiated instruction?
- (2) What is the posttest of Araling Panlipunan 7 students both controlled and experimental groups after the implementation of differentiated instruction?
- (3) Is there a significant difference of the academic performance between controlled and experimental groups after the implementation of video clips?

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

Fig. 2. Gantt Chart

- (4) What is the magnitude effect of differentiated instruction on the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The Null Hypothesis in this study tested at 0.05 level of significance. HO1. The differentiated instruction has no significant relationship in the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students. HO2. Differentiated instruction has no magnitude effect on academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students.

1.6. Significance of the Study—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study. DepEd Officials. The result of this study will reveal the level of impact of differentiated instruction and how it affects the Araling Panlipunan 7 students academic performance. Moreover, this research will provide the foundation for DepEd Officials to organize a range of seminars and pertinent training programs across multiple fields on the implementation of differentiated instruction, particularly in enhancing the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students. School Administrators. The findings of this study are beneficial to the school head of Sta. Cruz National High School. They school head can utilize the vital information from this research study to utilize differentiated instruction that will directly affect the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students. As instructional leaders, school heads

are tasked to implement different instructions to promote teachers' pedagogy in realizing the learning institutions' goals, missions, and visions. Teachers. The findings of this research study are helpful to teachers of Sta. Cruz National School as how they will employ the utilization of differentiated instruction in enhancing the academic performance of Araling Panlipunan 7 students. As teachers, simple teaching strategies is enough to create a more inclusive and equitable learning environment. Future Researchers. The findings of this study may encourage them to conduct similar studies in other areas. This study serves as an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study. Definition of Terms To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. Differentiated Instruction refers to an approach to teaching and learning that recognizes and accommodates the diverse needs of students. It allows teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the individual needs, interests, and learning styles of each student. Academic Performance refers to how well a student is doing in their studies. It is a reflection of a student's knowledge, skills, effort, and motivation in their studies.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

01 X 02

03 X 04

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the control group
- 04 Posttest of the control group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School, Sta.Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 85 grade four pupils – 42 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 43 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	42
2	Section B	43
Total		87

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners online for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 45 –item test will eventually determine the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess academic performance of the grade seven students. On the hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the level of academic performance of the grade 7 students, the following continuum used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Sta. Cruz National High School. While letters sought for permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts

Grading Scale

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects was submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after

which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean used to describe the level of the academic performance of the learners in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square used to measure the magnitude of differentiated instruction on the academic performance of the grade 7 students.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade six

learners. The controlled group got the mean of 67.93 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 69.91 or Beginning.

Table 1:Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group (Pre-test)	42	30.57	67.93	Beginning
Experimental Group (Pre-test)	43	31.46	69.91	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Werderich (2020) who said that Learners acquire and process knowledge in many manners. Educators must employ a wide range of instructional strategies to accommodate the learning preferences of individual students. Students can enhance their academic performance and attitudes toward learning if they are able to identify their unique learning styles and are taught accordingly. In

a differentiated classroom, the teacher designs and implements multiple approaches to material, process, and output in anticipation of and in response to student variances in readiness, interest, and learning requirements. She also classified differentiated components in a classroom as content, method, and products. The content relates to "what to teach" and is what students gain or learn. Process focuses on "how to teach" the concepts and abilities that students must acquire. The product reflects the individual perception of the learners and illustrates their knowledge (Cohen, 2021).

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group (Pre-test)	42	30.57	Beginning
Experimental Group (Pre-test)	43	31.46	Beginning

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade six learners. The controlled group got the mean of 36.20 or Beginning while the experimental group gained the mean of 38.08 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.62 from a mean rating of 31.46 to 38.08. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Valiandes (2019) who cited that learners made greater progress in classes where differentiated instruction methods were systematically implemented, as compared to classrooms where differentiated instruction methods were not consistently employed. According to the findings,

the quality of differentiated instruction provided by the teacher has a significant impact on student achievement, as does the systematic use of differentiated instruction methods in mixed ability classrooms for promoting equity, optimizing quality, and maximizing teaching effectiveness. Learning styles as "personal characteristics that influence a student's ability to acquire information, connect with peers and the teacher, and overall engage in learning activities." Identifying learning styles enables a teacher to focus on a student's abilities and familiarize themselves with ideas that may be difficult for them (Tilston, 2020). Every student will realize their full potential when they are provided with opportunities for authentic learning based on their interests and needs; consequently, the benefits are substantial. Teachers who are uninformed

of student learning styles are likely to instruct in a manner that discourages students from achieving their full potential (Wan, 2020).

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post- Test Score.

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.42	.0373	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.42 with a p-value of .0373 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade 7 students. This implies that the used of differentiated instruction in teaching Araling Panlipunan Seven have contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the grade seven students. This finding is in line with the statement of Kadum-Bošnjak (2020) who said that differentiated instruction has a favorable impact on student performance. It increased performance and had an impact on student achievement, and it is highly recommended that teachers utilizing differentiated instruction present a learning style inventory to their students before adopting differenti-

ated instruction since this inventory will provide the instructor with the required information on how to differentiate lessons according to the students' preferences and interests. The differentiated classroom will assist the teacher in addressing the academic demands of each student. In a differentiated classroom, there is no place for fear, and students are free to take risks with their learning. By structuring lessons according to students' readiness levels, interests, and learning profiles, teachers will be able to incorporate students' existing knowledge and experiences from outside the school setting. This will enable students to perceive things differently and offer their perspectives because they are already knowledgeable about the issue and have an interest in it. Lessons are modified to appropriately challenge students, hence eliminating hassles and boredom (Brimijoin, 2020).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 7 Students

N	t-value	Eta ²	Descriptive Value	Decision
85	-4.46	0.432	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of Role Play approach on the historical appreciation skills of grade five learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.432 which signifies large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in teaching Araling Panlipunan as it plays a vital role in shaping students' understanding of

their nation's history, culture, society, and government. Students bring their varied cultural backgrounds, styles of learning, preferences, capabilities, and various intelligences to the classroom. When it concerns to serving the needs of all students, the diversity of children in the classroom can pose a considerable barrier for

teachers. Some pupils may find the lesson too easy, while others may find it too difficult; some students may find the topic engaging, while others may find it uninteresting. The purpose of differentiated instruction (DI) is to tailor the lesson to each student's learning styles, interests, skills, and multiple intelligences (Shearer, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of differentiated instruction in Araling Panlipunan 7 on the academic performance of the students. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz National High School, Sta. Cruz South District Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 85 grade seven learners – 42 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 43 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the utilization of differentiated instruction in Araling Panlipunan 7 has increased the academic performance of grade seven learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade seven learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching Araling Panlipunan seven should used differentiated instruction as a strategy that would further develop the academic performance of learners in order to make the teaching of Araling Panlipunan meaningful. By tailoring instruction to meet individual needs, this approach promotes inclusivity, fosters engagement and motivation, supports academic growth, cultivates a positive classroom culture, and empowers teachers to effectively meet the needs of all students. The school heads should promote the use of differentiated instruction as a strategy that would cater to the diverse needs of all learners as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially on subjects that talks about history, culture, geography, and society. A school policy about the utilization of differentiated instruction in Araling Panlipunan can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session using play as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of differentiated instruction as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Anderson, K. M. (2019). Tips for teaching: Differentiating instruction to include all students. *Preventing School Failure: Alternative Education for Children and Youth*.
- Beecher, M. (2020). Closing the achievement gap with curriculum enrichment and differentiation: One school's story. *Journal of Advanced Academics*.
- Benjamin, A. (2021). Valuing differentiated instruction. *Journal of Philippine Education*.
- Betts, G. (2019). Fostering autonomous learners through levels of differentiation. *Roeper Review*.
- Brimijoin, K. (2020). Differentiation and high-stakes testing: An oxymoron. *International Research in Education*.
- Brookhart, S. (2008). *How to give effective feedback to your students*. Action in Teacher Education.
- Campbell, B. (2019). Differentiated instruction for middle and high school educators. *Development for Educators Conference*.
- Cohen, R. (2021). Unlocking the gate to differentiation. *Journal for the Education of the Gifted*.
- Dee, A. L. (2019). Preservice teacher application of differentiated instruction. *Teacher Educator*.
- Doll, W. E. (2019). *A post-modern perspective on curriculum*. Teachers College Press.
- DuFour, R. (2019). What is a "professional learning community?" *Teaching Exceptional Children*.
- Dunn, K. J. (2020). Teaching elementary students through their individual learning styles. *Journal of Advanced Academics*.
- Flemming, L. (2020). *Differentiating in the classroom: A study of student teachers*. Teachers College Press.
- Goddard, Y. (2020). A multilevel exploratory study of the relationship between teachers' perceptions of principals' instructional support and group norms for instruction in elementary schools. *The Elementary School Journal*.
- Gonzalez, A. B. (2019). Personal interview on the challenges and opportunities of implementing education for all in rural areas [University of the Philippines, Quezon City, Philippines].
- Goodnough, K. (2019). Investigating pre-service science teachers' developing professional knowledge through the lens of differentiated instruction. *Research in Science Education*.
- Gregory, G. H. (2005). *Differentiating instruction with style*. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Hattie, J. (2019). Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement. *Learning Disability Quarterly*.
- Joseph, S. (2021). The impact of differentiated instruction in a teacher education setting: Successes and challenges. *International Journal of Higher Education*.
- Kadum-Bošnjak, S. (2020). Impact of differentiated instruction on achievement in teaching mathematics to lower-stage grades. *A Journal of Educational Strategies*.
- Kiley, D. (2019). Differentiated instruction in the secondary classroom: Analysis of the level of implementation and factors that influence practice. *Educational Practice and Theory*.
- Langa, M. A. (2020). Curriculum mapping for differentiated instruction. *International Education Studies*.
- Levy, H. M. (2019). Meeting the needs of all students through differentiated instruction: Helping every child reach and exceed standards. *Educational Research Journals*.
- Logan, B. (2019). Examining differentiated instruction: Teachers respond. *Research in Higher Education Journal*.

- Melesse, T. (2020). Differentiated instruction: Perceptions, practices and challenges of primary school teachers. *Science, Technology and Arts Research Journal*.
- Mellard, D. F. (2020). Rti: A practitioner's guide to implementing response to intervention. *Roepers Review*.
- Morrison, F. J. (2020). Testing the impact of child characteristics and instruction interactions on third graders' reading comprehension by differentiating literacy instruction. *Reading Research Quarterly*.
- Page, S. (2007). Choosing a differentiation focus for my school or district plan. *Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development*.
- Patterson, J. L. (2020). Restructuring the inclusion classroom to facilitate differentiated instruction. *Middle School Journal*.
- Pettig, K. L. (2020). On the road to differentiated practice. *Educational Leadership*.
- Renzulli, J. S. (2019). The multiple menu model for developing differentiated curriculum for the gifted and talented. *Gifted Child Quarterly*.
- Reynolds, T. (2021). Differentiating instruction in response to student readiness, interest, and learning profile in academically diverse classrooms: A review of literature. *Journal for the Education of the Gifted*.
- Rhoad, R. (2020). Meeting diverse student needs in urban schools: Research-based recommendations for school personnel. *Journal in Preventing School Failure*.
- Santangelo, T. (2020). Teacher educators' perceptions and use of differentiated instruction practices: An exploratory investigation. *Action in Teacher Education Journal*.
- Schumer, F. (2019). A paddle for the mainstream. *Learning Disability Quarterly*.
- Shearer, B. (2020). Multiple intelligences after 20 years. *Teachers College Record*.
- Simpkins, P. M. (2019). Differentiated curriculum enhancements in inclusive fifth-grade science classes. *Remedial and Special Education*.
- Tileston, D. (2020). *What every teacher should know about special learners*.
- Valiandes, S. (2019). Teachers' professional development for differentiated instruction in mixed-ability classrooms: Investigating the impact of a development program on teachers' professional learning and on students' achievement. *Teacher Development*.
- Wan, S. W. (2020). Differentiated instruction: Hong kong prospective teachers' teaching efficacy and beliefs. *Teachers and Teaching*.
- Werderich, D. E. (2020). Individualized responses: Using journal letters as a vehicle for differentiated reading instruction. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*.
- Witherell, N. L. (2019). Different routes to the same destination: Drawing conclusions with tiered graphic organizers. *The Reading Teacher*.
- Yendol-Hoppey, D. (2020). Teacher learning through self-regulation: An exploratory study of alternatively prepared teachers' ability to plan differentiated instruction in an urban elementary school. *Teacher Education Quarterly*.